

Study of binary and ternary metal-2-chlorobenzoate complexes by ionophoretic technique

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Abstract : Use of an ionophoretic technique is described here for the study of equilibria in binary and ternary complex systems in solution. For the study of ternary complexes, the concentration of one of the complexants 2-chloro benzoic acid is kept constant, while that of the other nitrilotriacetate (NTA) is varied. The overall stability constants of M-2-chlorobenzoic acid and M-2-chlorobenzoic-NTA complexes were found to be $10^{3.84}$, $10^{2.71}$, $10^{2.64}$ and $10^{2.59}$ for binary and $10^{6.69}$, $10^{6.65}$, $10^{6.45}$ and $10^{6.20}$ for ternary Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes respectively at $\mu = 0.1 M$ and 25 °C.

Keywords : Binary complex, ternary complex, stability constant, ionophoretic technique.

In the present communication an effort has been made to assess the stability constants of metal complexes with a single ligand along with the systematic study of ternary complexes formed in a system containing various electrolyte ingredients. A simple ionophoretic tube¹ has been designed for this work, which yields better results after standardization.

Results and discussion

Metal-2-chlorobenzoic acid system :

The relationship between absorbance difference and the pH's gives an idea of the change of overall mobility of the metal ion species with change in hydrogen ion status of the system containing Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} 2-chlorobenzoic acid. Further increase of pH from this region onward which naturally leads to increase in ligating 2-chlorobenzoic acid anion concentration [HL⁻] and brings about a progressive decrease in overall ionic mobility of the metal ion species. This decrease indicates formation of complex of the metal ion with the ligand. A point is reached beyond which mobility of the metal ion species remain constant regardless of the increase of pH of reaction mixture. This is the region in which 1 : 1 complex is predominantly formed. Beyond this increase of pH has no effect and mobility remain constant.

Metal-2-chlorobenzoic acid-NTA system :

Fig. 1 depicts the observation of studies carried out in 2-chlorobenzoic acid-NTA ternary complexes. These graphs

clearly show the formation of two plateaus in each cases. The first plateau corresponds to binary M-2-chlorobenzoic acid complexes whereas the second plateau corresponds to the formation of new complex.

This new complex may be mixed complexes of the type M-L-NTA or pure M-NTA complex. But with the help of related graphs of M-NTA complexes it was found that the absorbance difference in case of new complex is not identical to M-NTA pure complex. Further this ternary complex has greater mobility than that of binary 2-chlorobenzoic acid complex, hence these observations confirm the formation of mixed M-L-NTA complex.

Stability constants : Binary metal-2-chlorobenzoic acid system :

The overall mobility U is a composite parameter contributed by different ionic species of the metal ion and is given by following equation :

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K_1 [L] + u_2 K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + \dots}{1 + K_1 [L] + K_1 K_2 [L]^2 + \dots}$$

where K 's are the stability constant of complexes and $[L]$ is the concentration of 2-chlorobenzoic acid anion. u 's are the ionic mobilities of different species of the metal ions which can be assessed from the plateau's of the figure. In the region between first and second plateau the system contains overwhelmingly a mixture of free metal ion and 1 : 1 complex. The existence of 1 : 2 complex can be excluded and

hence the third term in the numerator and the denominator of the above equation can be justifiably neglected. U would be equal to $(u_0 + u_1)/2$ provided $K_1[L] = 1$. Accordingly the pH corresponding to the average value of u_0 and u_1 is found from the figure and with the knowledge of the dissociation constants of 2-chlorobenzoic acid ($pK_1 = 2.92$)² the concentration of 2-chlorobenzoic acid ion at this pH is calculated. Its reciprocal gives the stability constant K_1 of the 1 : 1 complex. The values of the stability constants are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Stability constants of metal-2-chlorobenzoic acid and M-2-chlorobenzoic acid-NTA complexes

Ionic strength $\mu = 0.1 M$, Temp. = 25 °C

Metal ion	Stability constant values	
	K M M-L	K' M-L M-L-NTA
Fe ^{III}	3.84	6.69
Cu ^{II}	2.71	6.65
Ni ^{II}	2.64	6.45
Co ^{II}	2.60	6.20

Metal-2-chlorobenzoic acid-NTA ternary system :

For M-L-NTA complexes the stability constant K' is calculated by using modified equation.

$$U = \frac{U_0 + U_1 K' [NTA^-]}{1 + K' [NTA^-]}$$

here U_0 and U_1 are the mobilities of ML and M-L-NTA complexes.

From the figures concentration of NTA at which overall

mobility is the mean of the mobilities of the two plateaus is determined. The concentration of NTA anion at pH 7.0 for this NTA concentration is calculated. K' is obviously equal to $1/[NTA]$. All these values are also reported in Table 1 which clearly indicate the superior coordinating power of NTA anion to other dicarboxylic acid species.

The stability constant values of Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} are in the order : Fe^{III} > Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II}, which follows the Irving-William's³ order for the stability constant of transition metals of first transition series.

Experimental

The technique consisted in carrying electrophoresis in background electrolyte containing 0.1 M perchloric acid and $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ 2-chlorobenzoic acid/ $0.2 \times 10^{-2} M$ NTA with metal ion Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} and NaOH was added to produce the desired pH for the study of binary complexes. In each electrophoretic observations electrolysis was carried out for 45 min at 50 V at 25 °C.

For the study of ternary complexes the experimental procedure was slightly modified. Here the background electrolyte contained secondary ligand (NTA) in addition to primary ligand (2-chlorobenzoic acid). For the ternary complexes the pH was always maintained at 7.0 (by adding NaOH solution) and concentration of secondary ligand (NTA) ranged from 10^{-6} to $10^{-2} M$.

Procedure for binary complexes : Metal-2-chlorobenzoic acid system :

A set of 15 ml solution each containing $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ Cu^{II},

Fig. 1. Mobility curve. Metal-2-chlorobenzoic acid-NTA system.

Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, 0.1 M HClO₄ and 1 × 10⁻² M 2-chlorobenzoic acid was used. In case of Fe^{III}, 1 × 10⁻⁴ M Fe^{III}, 0.1 M HClO₄ and 1 × 10⁻³ M 2-chlorobenzoic acid was used. 10 ml of this solution is taken in an electrophoretic tube and thermostated at 25°. The tube (18 cm × 5 mm dia) was adjusted in such a way that the level of the solution in one wide end arm reached a circular mark on it. This adjustment fixed the volume of the solution on both sides of the middle stopper. Two platinum electrodes (0.5 cm × 0.5 cm) were dipped in each arm cup and 50 V potential difference was applied between them. Electrolysis of the solution was allowed for 45 min after which the middle stopper of the tube was closed. The solution of anodic compartment was taken in a 15 ml flask. The copper content of the solution was converted into copper thiocyanate⁴. The volume was raised to a mark in the flask and the absorbance at 408 nm was measured with CZ-specol spectrophotometer. The Ni^{II} content of the solution was converted to nickel dimethyl glyoximate⁵ complex and absorbance was taken at 445 nm. The Co^{II} content of the anodic compartment was converted into cobalt thiocyanate⁴ complex and absorbance at 625 nm was measured after making up the volume to 15 ml. Similarly the Fe^{III} content of the anodic compartment was converted to ferric thiocyanate⁵ complex and absorbance was measured at 480 nm against a reagent blank at different pH's.

Procedure for the ternary complexes : An appropriate reaction mixture containing metal ions and 2-chlorobenzoic acid and 0.1 M perchloric acid was adjusted to pH 7.0 and the secondary ligand was added progressively and the

absorbance was measured as it was done for binary system. The absorbance difference was plotted against -log [NTA] and these observations are graphically represented in Fig. 1. Under a potential gradient, a metal ion will move in the field. The speed and its direction depend upon the charge and size of the ion.

In case of binary complex the metal ion may be assumed to have ligated with a ligand to give complex as :

In case of ternary complexes the interaction of secondary ligand NTA with the binary metal complex can be shown as :

where M is metal ion, 2-chlorobenzoic acid is primary ligand and NTA act as secondary ligand.

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